

INDICATORS AND INHERITANCE OF STEM LENGTH AND POD LENGTH TRAITS IN INITIAL SOURCES OF THE *PHASEOLUS AUREUS* L. AND F₁ HYBRIDS

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Annotation. This article presents an analysis of the indicators obtained for stem length and pod length in initial sources of the *Phaseolus aureus* L. species and their F₁ hybrids. Regarding these traits in the initial sources, the local "Turon" (Uzbekistan) sample expressed the highest values for both traits with a stem length of 62 cm and a pod length of 10 cm. Several foreign samples showed lower values for these traits, including "K-418" (Philippines), "K-599" (India), "K-2" (China), and "K-338" (China), which had a stem length of 33 cm and a pod length of 5 cm. In the F₁ plants obtained as a result of hybridization, heterosis was mainly observed.

Key words: mung bean, pod, combination, heterosis (known as hybrid vigor), inheritance, dominant, yield, productivity, variety, cultivar, seed, hybrid.

Introduction

Globally, in these days, leguminous grain crops are cultivated as a second crop on 91.6 million hectares, with an average grain yield of 1.2 tons/ha and a total production of 206.4 million tons. In our republic, however, more than 18-25 thousand hectares are planted annually as a second crop. India is the leading country in mung bean production and consumption. Uzbekistan also plays a significant role in the global mung bean export market, exporting up to 67 thousand tons annually [1].

Mung bean is a heat-loving crop. Seeds begin to germinate when the soil temperature is 12-15 °C. The optimal temperature for seed germination is 20-25 °C. The growing season lasts 80-110 days depending on the variety, agricultural practices, and planting time. The plant dies when the temperature reaches -1 °C. It is a moisture-loving plant and is mainly cultivated on irrigated lands in Uzbekistan [2].

Mung bean (*Phaseolus aureus* L.) has been cultivated in India since ancient times. The origin of mung bean is Southwestern Asia, and its agricultural cultivation began 5-6 thousand years ago. Currently, this crop is grown in large volumes in India, Pakistan, Afghanistan, Iran, Myanmar, China, Vietnam, Japan, African countries, South American countries, and Australia. Mung bean is planted as a main crop or as a second crop after winter wheat (on small areas) in Uzbekistan, Turkmenistan, Tajikistan, the Caucasus, and Southern Kazakhstan. Its stem is herbaceous, angular, highly branched, climbing or prostrate, reaching a height of 15-120 cm, with an average of 30-60 cm, and branches well. The stem color is light green or yellowish-green, and it can be hairy or hairless depending on the variety. Lateral branches are divided into monopodia (growing) branches that develop from the bottom to the top of the stem and sympodia (fruit-bearing) branches that develop from the top to the bottom [1].

The pods shatter, but newly introduced (initial stage of acclimatization) erect varieties have white downy hairs inside the pods, which prevents them from shattering and the grains from shedding. Their husks are hard (parchment shell) and thick. Each plant can have an average of 46-78 pods, and each pod contains an average of 8-12 mung bean seeds [4].

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In natural conditions, the growth and development of plants are influenced by environmental factors. External environmental factors (light, water, air, nutrients) are equally important for plants, and one cannot be substituted for another. Although natural factors are of equal value for plant life in terms of their physiological impact, they have different effects on their life processes and developmental stages. The growth, development, plant height, yield, quality, and formation period are the result of the complex interaction between the physiological processes occurring in the plant and the external environment.

The degree of dominance of traits in the studied first-generation hybrids was calculated according to the S. Wright formula presented in the works of G.E. Beil and R.E. Atkins [5].

$$hp = \frac{F_1 - MP}{P - MP}$$

hp – dominance coefficient;

F₁ – mean arithmetic indicator of hybrid;

MP – mean arithmetic indicator of both parental forms;

P – mean arithmetic indicator of best parental form.

hp = 0 – no dominance;

0 < hp < ±1,0 – moderate dominance;

hp = ±1,0 – complete dominance;

hp > ±1,0 – overdominance.

Research object and methods. The research was conducted at Chirchik State Pedagogical University. The research objects included samples of the mung bean plant (*Phaseolus aureus* L.) such as "K-2" (China), "K-236" (Manchuria), "K-338" (China), "K-413" (Vietnam), "K-414" (Vietnam), "K-418" (Philippines), "K-599" (India), "K-716" (Afghanistan), "K-181" (Taiwan), "K-255" (India), "K-489" (Local Uzbekistan), as well as the varieties "Turon" (Uzbekistan), "Durdona" (Uzbekistan), and F₁ hybrids.

Fig. 1. Inheritance and variability of the stem length trait in initial forms and F₁ plants.

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The degree of inheritance of plant height in parental and F₁ hybrids of *Phaseolus aureus* L. varied. Among the initial sources, the "Turon" (Uzbekistan) sample had the longest stem at 62 cm, while the lowest value was observed in the foreign sample "K-2" (China) at 33 cm. Regarding the stem length indicators of the F₁ combinations obtained as a result of hybridization, the highest result was observed in the F₁ "K-181" (Taiwan) x "Turon" (Uzbekistan) combination, reaching 70 cm, with this trait showing inheritance in an overdominant state (hp=5). The lowest indicator, 50 cm, was recorded in the F₁ "Turon" x "Philippines", F₁ "China-338" x "Vietnam-414", and F₁ "Vietnam-414" x "Vietnam-413" combination samples.

Regarding the stem length indicators of the F₁ combinations obtained as a result of hybridization, the highest result was observed in the F₁ "K-181" (Taiwan) x "Turon" (Uzbekistan) combination, reaching 70 cm, with this trait showing inheritance in an overdominant state (hp=5). The lowest indicator, 50 cm, was recorded in the F₁ "Turon" x "Philippines", F₁ "China-338" x "Vietnam-414", and F₁ "Vietnam-414" x "Vietnam-413" combination samples.

Fig. 2. Inheritance of the pod length trait in initial sources of the *Phaseolus aureus* L.

Conclusion

The degree of inheritance of pod length in parental and F₁ hybrids of *Phaseolus aureus* L. plants showed different patterns. Among the initial sources, the Turon (Uzbekistan) sample had the longest pods at 10 cm, while several foreign samples, including "K-418" (Philippines), "K-599" (India), "K-2" (China), and "K-338" (China), showed lower values at 5 cm. Regarding the pod length indicators of the F₁ combinations obtained as a result of hybridization, the highest result was observed in the F₁

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"K-181" (Taiwan) x "Turon" (Uzbekistan) combination, reaching 10.5 cm, with this trait showing inheritance in a positive intermediate state ($hp=0.43$). The lowest indicator, 6.36 cm, was recorded in the F_1 "K-414" (Vietnam) x "K-489" (Local Uzbekistan) combination sample, with this trait showing inheritance in an overdominant state ($hp=2.48$) (Fig. 2).

As a result of this research, it can be concluded that regarding the stem length indicators of the F_1 combinations obtained from the hybridization of initial sources belonging to the *Phaseolus aureus* L. species and their F_1 hybrids, the highest result was observed in the F_1 "K-181" (Taiwan) x "Turon" (Uzbekistan) combination, reaching 70 cm, with this trait showing inheritance in an overdominant state ($hp=5$). The lowest indicator, 50 cm, was recorded in the F_1 "Turon" x "Philippines", F_1 "China-338" x "Vietnam-414", and F_1 "Vietnam-414" x "Vietnam-413" combination samples. In the analysis of the pod length indicators, local and foreign samples are considered morphologically distant forms, and as a result of hybridization, the positive intermediate and overdominant inheritance of traits in them was observed.

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